

Effect of Outdoor Laboratory Strategy on Attitude and Performance in Ecology Concept among Secondary School Students in Kano State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of outdoor laboratory strategy on attitude, and performance in ecology concept among secondary schools in Kano State Nigeria. The study adopted a pre-test, post-test quasi-experimental control group design. The population of the study comprises all Senior Secondary Schools two biology students (SSII) during the 2023/2024 academic session in Kano State. A sample size of One hundred and twenty-three (123) SSII biology students were selected from the target population stratified random sampling technique. Stratified random sampling technique was used to select the sample size due to gender difference in senior secondary schools in Kano state. Four schools were randomly selected using balloting method, which involved hand picking from the container, two were females' schools and two were males' schools. A total of 62 students were in the experimental group and taught using outdoor laboratory strategy while 61 students were in the control group taught using lecture method. The two groups were taught ecology concepts for six weeks. Two instruments were used and these are; Ecology Performance Test (EPT) with reliability coefficient of $r = 0.98$ and Ecology Attitude Questionnaire (EAQ) with reliability coefficient of $r = 0.92$. Two null hypotheses were formulated to guide the researcher. The hypotheses were tested using t-test and U-test statistics at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance. The result of the analysis shows a significance difference exist in the two hypotheses. The researcher concluded that, Outdoor laboratory strategy has significant effect on attitude, and performance of students in ecology concept among secondary school students in Kano State. The researcher recommended that biology teachers in secondary school should be using Outdoor laboratory strategy.

Keywords: Outdoor Laboratory, Attitude, Performance and Ecology.

Introduction

Outdoor Laboratory is an instructional strategy that was first introduced in the 1920s and has its philosophical foundations laid by thinkers such as Rousseau, Pestalozzi, Comenius and Dewey. Outdoor Laboratory is one of the activity-based instructional strategies that take place outside the classroom, based on learning by doing. Maikano (2019) defined an Outdoor laboratory as a natural environment of living organisms such as fields, riversides, ponds, and trees among others where living things can best be studied from an ecological point of view. The outdoor laboratory is a student's centered strategy where the teacher acts as a facilitator of learning, guiding the students through a series of activities and problems which may help learners to achieve highly. The outdoor laboratory advocates the realization of learning where it can be done and where its purpose can be achieved, covers activities at elementary school, middle school, high school, and university levels and in many geographical settings (Gumus 2020). Outdoor learning environments can help students communicate with their peers, understand others, work together democratically, towards common goals, develop community awareness, and understand their place in the world. However, this method may affect the attitude of the students.

Attitude as one of the variables of the present study plays an important role in the academic performance of science students. Students' attitude towards biology affects their science academic performance because biology is one of the core science subjects. Erdemir and Bakirci (2014) described the attitude as the tendency of individuals who organize thoughts, emotions, and behaviours towards a psychological object. The concept of attitude arose from an attempt to account for observed regularities in the behaviour of an individual (Elijah, Lynn & Jonson; 2015). This attitude can be positive, negative or neutral

one's inner experiences are evidence of one's attitude. Therefore, when students experience some difficulties in learning biology they will manifest unfavorable or negative attitudes towards biology. Sakariyau (2016) recognized attitude as a major factor in the choice of subject and also considered attitude as a mental and natural state of readiness, organized through experiences exerting a directive influence upon the individual's responses to all objects and situations with which it is related. Attitude is like academic achievement because they are a significant factor in ensuring students' success. Science teachers need to ensure that students have positive attitudes toward science subjects. However, the favorable and positive attitude of students toward biology is facilitated by the use of a suitable instructional approach. To improve students' attitudes, teachers of biology have look a suitable and favorable instructional strategy that will enable the students to participate fully in class such as outdoor laboratory teaching strategy. But so unfortunate from experience by the researcher majority of the teachers of biology are using lecture method.

The lecture method which is predominantly used in senior secondary schools in Nigeria contributes to the poor academic performance of senior secondary school biology students in Nigeria (Ezenwoso, 2013). The lecture method is a teaching strategy which involved verbal presentation where the teacher delivers the lesson to the students with little or no active participation by the students. It is a teacher-centered approach which involved- way form of communication from the teacher to the students. This is why it is referred to as the didactic approach because it involved the verbal presentation of concepts, where the teacher presents, spoken and discourse on a particular subject while the students remain passive listeners and take down notes. The lecture method of teaching emphasizes "Talk and Chalk" in the teaching of science subjects' biology inclusive. More than 80% of the scientific information and principles are delivered as a lecture. Hence the teaching of ecology is faced with the dilemma of either using simplified or more complex materials. Therefore, teaching certain ecology concepts requires basic knowledge about the species involved and their natural environment. Usman (2010) observed that the lecture method encourages rote learning without proper understanding, thereby resulting in poor performance. However, the use of activity-based strategies such as field trips, problem-solving, cooperative learning strategy; guided discovery and outdoor laboratory may increase the performance of students, particularly slow learners.

Empirically the review some previous works of other researchers such as the work of Saidu and Suleman (2014) investigated the effects of outdoor laboratory teaching strategy on Academic performances among College of Education Students of different ability levels in North-west Zone Nigeria. The findings of their study showed that the outdoor laboratory teaching strategy favoured the experimental group.

Stanley (2019) investigated the impact of outdoor and indoor laboratory strategies on the retention of learnt ecological concepts among senior secondary school biology students in the Giwa education zone of Kaduna state, Nigeria. The findings of the reviewed study showed that Students exposed to the outdoor laboratory instructional strategy retained the learnt concepts significantly better than their counterparts exposed to the Indoor laboratory instructional strategy and taught ecology concept.

Donmez (2021), Investigated the impact of Out-of-School STEM Activities on the STEM Career Choices of Female Students who make university preferences after grade 11 in the Turkish education system. The findings revealed that the interest of the participants in STEM career fields differs significantly between pre- and post-STEM activities. These findings showed that the implementation of out-of-school STEM activities contributed to an increase in STEM career interest.

Hussaini, Foong and Kamar, (2015), investigated the Attitudes of Secondary School students towards biology as a school subject in Birnin Kebbi Metropolitan, Kebbi State, Nigeria. The finding showed that the differences between the attitudes of male and female students were significantly insignificant.

Sakariyau (2015) studied the Attitudes of Secondary School Students towards Biology in the Odeda Local Government Area of Ogun State, Nigeria. The finding showed that a higher proportion of the students display a positive attitude towards science.

Aminu (2017) determined the Effect of Social Constructivism Instructional Strategy on attitude, and Performance in the Algebraic process among SSII Students in Sokoto state, Nigeria. A quasi-experimental design was used. The findings indicated that there were statistically significantly different in the mean scores of the experimental and control group in performance and retention. Sofiani, Maulida, Fadhillah and Sihite (2017) investigated the students' attitudes towards science and the effect of gender in Bundung, Indonesia. Their findings showed that students' positive attitude towards science was at medium level and there was no significant difference in attitude towards science between the female and male.

Zakariya (2017) studied the Impact of Metacognitive Strategy on Attitude, Retention and Performance in Calculus among Colleges of Education Students in the North-central Zone, of Nigeria. The study adopted a Pre-test, Post-test, and post-post-test quasi-experimental design. The findings revealed that there was a significant difference between the post-test mean scores of the experimental and control groups in favour of the experimental group. Out of the reviewed the most resent is the work of Donmez (2021) while the present work is conducted is this year 2024 and also none of the work was conducted in Kano state. Also none of the work used outdoor laboratory strategy on students' performance and attitude in ecology.

In order to give students room for participation and learning from each other the researcher intend to find out the effect of outdoor laboratory strategy on students, attitude and performance in ecology among secondary school students in Kano state, Nigeria. To achieve this objective, the researcher design to achieve the following specific objectives as follows:

Objectives of the Study

The following objectives were raised to guide study.

1. Determine the effect of outdoor laboratory strategy on students' attitude in ecology among secondary school students in Kano state, Nigeria
2. Examine the effect of outdoor laboratory strategy on students' Performance in ecology among secondary school students in Kano state, Nigeria

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide study.

1. What are the mean difference between the students' attitude taught ecology concept using outdoor laboratory strategy and those taught using lecture methods in Kano State?
2. What are the mean difference between the students' performance taught ecology concept using outdoor laboratory strategy and those taught using lecture methods in Kano State?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to be tested at $P \leq 0,05$ level of significance

H₀₁: There is no significance difference between the students' attitude taught ecology using outdoor laboratory strategy and those taught using lecture methods in Kano State.

H₀₂: There is no significance difference between the students' performance taught ecology using outdoor laboratory strategy and those taught using lecture methods in Kano State.

Methodology

The design adapted for this study is quasi- experimental control groups research design as recommended by Kerlinger (1973). Two groups were considered for this study. The two groups were pre-tested with (EPT) in order to determine the equivalence of students' ability level of the two groups. The Population of the study comprises the entire public Senior Secondary Schools two, (SSII) biology students in Dawakin Kudu Education Zone, Kano State. There are 36 senior secondary schools in Dawakin Kudu Education Zone, which consist of single sex secondary schools. Records of enrolment showed that, 5185 students as the tagged population that comprised 3392 boys and 1793 girls. The sample size of 123 Biology students were used which is in line with the central limit theory that recommends minimum of 30 samples as variable for the experimental research (Tukman 1975). Thus, 123 biology samples were obtained through the use of stratified random sampling technique and were considered appropriate for the research study as pointed out by Sambo, (2008). Two instruments were used namely Ecology Attitude Questionnaire (EAQ) and Ecology Performance Test (EPT), the two instruments were validated by expert in science education and the reliability of the two instruments were obtain were 0.98 and 0.92 using crombach- α and Pearson Product Moment Correlation. A treatment was given to the experimental group by exposing them to outdoor laboratory strategies for six weeks and control groups was taught ecology concepts with lecture method only for same numbers of weeks. At the end of six weeks' treatment a post-test was administered to both groups (experimented and control) using EAQ and EPT. The scripts were collected and mark by the researcher and recorded it tables for data analysis. The data were analyzed using t-test and U-test statistics. The result of the analyses is presented as follows.

Research Question One: What are mean difference between the students' attitude taught ecology conceptusing outdoor laboratory strategy and those taught using lecture methods?

To answer the research question one, mean and standard deviation were used. The detail of the result is presented in Table 1:

Table 1: Summary of Post-test Attitude Mean Rank and Sum of Rank Scores of Students in the Experimental and Control Groups

Variable	Group	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Mean Gain
Attitude	Experimental	62	68.19	4227.50	12.48

Control Group	61	55.71	3398.50
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Table 1 present the mean rank and sum of ranks scores of students in the experimental and control groups. The computed mean rank scores are 68.19 for students in the experimental group and 55.71 for students in the control group respectively. In the same vein, the computed sum of ranks scores is 4227.50 and 3398.50 for students in the experimental and control groups respectively. A mean rank gain of 12.48 was obtained in favour of students in the experimental group. The testing of the corresponding hypothesis is as follows:

H₀₁: There is no significance difference between the students’ attitude taught ecology concept using outdoor laboratory strategy and those taught using lecture methods.

To test the null hypothesis two, a Mann-Whitny U-test statistic was used. The summary of the analysis is presented in Table 2

Table 2: Summary of Mann-Whitney U-test Analysis of Post-test Scores for Students’ Attitude in the Experimental and Control Group

Groups	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	df	U-test	p-value	Decision
Experimental	62	68.19	4227.50	121	1507.50	0.05	rejected
Control	61	55.71	3398.50				
Total	123						

Significant at $P \leq 0.05$ level

Table 2 shows the summary of Mann-Whitny U-test analysis of experimental and control groups with U-test value of 1507.50 and p-value of 0.05 at df. of 121. This shows that, the p-value of 0.05 is equal to α –value of 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, with this evidence the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, there is significant difference in the attitudinal change of students taught ecology concepts using outdoor Laboratory strategy and those taught using lecture methods. This explain that, the experimental group develop more positive attitude than that of the control group as a result of the treatment given to the experimental group using outdoor Laboratory strategy. Therefore, outdoor Laboratory is capable of improving students’ attitude toward ecology concept.

Research Question Two: What are the mean difference between the performances of students taught ecology concepts using outdoor Laboratory and those taught with lecture method?

To answer the research question two, mean and standard deviation were used. The detail of the result is presented in Table 3

Table 3 : Mean and Mean Difference in the Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference
Experimental	62	23.63	4.39	11.3
Control	61	12.33	3.45	

Table 3 showed that, the mean performance score of students in experimental group was 23.63 with standard deviation 4.39 while the mean performance scores of students in the control group was 12.33 with standard deviation 3.45 and the mean difference was 11.3. This indicated that, there is difference between the mean performance scores of students exposed to Outdoor Laboratory and those exposed to lecture method. The testing of the corresponding hypothesis is as follows:

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the performances of students taught ecology concepts using outdoor Laboratory and those taught with lecture method.

To test the hypothesis two, independent t-test was used and the summary of the analysis is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Independent Samples t-test Analysis of Mean Performance Scores between Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	Mean	Std. D	Df	t _{cal}	P-value	Remark
Experimental	62	23.63	4.39	120	15.78	0.00	Significant
Control	60	12.33	3.45				

Significant at $P \leq 0.05$ level

Table 4 present the summary of t-test analysis with t_{cal} of 15.78 and P-value of 0.00 at df. of 120. This shows that, the P-value of 0.00 is less than the α –value of 0.05 level of significance. Based on this evidence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference between the performances of students taught ecology concepts using Outdoor Laboratory strategy and those taught with lecture method. This shows that, the treatment given to the experimental group has significance effect on the students' performance in ecology concept.

Discussion of Findings

The result of Table 2 revealed that, there was significance difference between the students' attitude taught ecology concept using outdoor laboratory strategy and those taught using lecture methods. in favour of experimental group. The finding of this study is in agreement with the finding of Sofiani, Maulida, Fadhillah and Sihite (2017) investigated the students' attitudes towards science and the effect of gender in Bundung, Indonesia. Their findings showed that students' positive attitude towards science was at medium level and there was no significant difference in attitude towards science between the female and male. In addition, Sakariyau (2015) studied the Attitudes of Secondary School Students towards Biology in the Odeda Local Government Area of Ogun State, Nigeria. The finding showed that a higher proportion of the students display a positive attitude towards science.

The result of Table 4 revealed that, there was a significant difference in the attitude means scores of students after been taught ecology concepts using outdoor Laboratory and those taught using lecture methods in favour of experimental group. The finding of this study is in agreement with the finding of Stanley (2019) investigated the impact of outdoor and indoor laboratory strategies on the retention of learnt ecological concepts among senior secondary school biology students in the Giwa education zone of Kaduna state, Nigeria. The findings of the reviewed study showed that Students exposed to the outdoor laboratory instructional strategy retained the learnt concepts significantly better than their counterparts exposed to the Indoor laboratory instructional strategy and taught ecology concept. His finding revealed that, outdoor laboratory instructional strategy contributed to the development of students' attitude and improved their performance. In addition, Muhammad (2017) who investigated the Effect of outdoor Laboratory and Peer Tutoring strategies on Attitude and Performance in Geometry among Secondary Schools Students in Niger state, Nigeria. His finding showed that, the students taught using outdoor laboratory and peer tutoring strategy develop high positive attitude than their counterpart who were taught with lecture method. The significant difference found between the two groups is likely due to the used of cooperative learning enriched with outdoor laboratory on the experimental group. Also Saidu and Suleman (2014) investigated the effects of outdoor laboratory teaching strategy on Academic performances among College of Education Students of different ability levels in North-west Zone Nigeria. The findings of their study showed that the outdoor laboratory teaching strategy favoured the experimental group.

Conclusion

Based on the findings obtained from this study, the following conclusions were reached: The researchers concluded that outdoor Laboratory is effective in improving academic performances in ecology concepts. Also the study concluded that Outdoor Laboratory help students in developing positive attitude towards teaching and learning of ecology concepts.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it was recommended that:

1. The Kano ministry of education should have emphasized the implementation of outdoor Laboratory strategy in teaching biology in secondary schools in order to improve the attitude students toward learning ecology concept.
2. The biology teachers in Kano State should start using outdoor Laboratory strategy in teaching biology in secondary schools in order to improve the students' performance in ecology.

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